

AGRO-TOURISM AND ITS IMPACT ON AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

Odiljanov Islomjon Ravshan ogli

Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of agrotourism on the agricultural economy. Agrotourism provides new opportunities for creating an additional source of income in rural areas, developing infrastructure and bringing agricultural products to markets. It is also an important factor in increasing employment in rural areas, reducing migration and supporting environmentally sustainable agriculture. The article also comments on the development prospects of agrotourism and its role in the agricultural economy.

Key words: agrotourism, agriculture, economic impact, additional income, infrastructure development, employment, environmental sustainability, rural culture, tourism.

In the following years, the share of agriculture in the GDP decreased due to the rapid growth of other sectors of the economy. Structural changes in agriculture, the emergence of farmers and peasant farms as the main producers of food products, and changes in the types of agricultural enterprises also affected this. As a result of the integration of tourism, which is becoming one of the leading and stable sectors of the economy, into the low-income sector, i.e., agriculture, the increase in the income of rural residents is proven in international experiences. In this regard, the issues listed in the Decree No. PF-5781 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, adopted on August 13, 2019, "On measures to further develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan" are the result of reforms to increase tourism potential.

According to it, it is necessary to solve the existing problems in the tourism infrastructure, increase the quality of the provided services and actively promote

national tourism products in the world markets, increase the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the tourism sector by strengthening the personnel potential of the tourism network, and increase the number of foreign citizens entering the republic. "Concept of development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025" was developed in order to dramatically increase.

Today, the growth and development of agriculture-based tourism is becoming an important tool in many countries to ensure economic stability, develop the infrastructure of rural areas, and retain the population in rural areas. It creates an additional source of income for the population living in rural areas and helps them improve their living conditions. This article analyzes the impact of agrotourism on the agricultural economy, its social and economic aspects, and future development prospects.

Agrotourism is aimed at showing rural life and agricultural activities to tourists through the provision of tourism services by farmers and farmers in rural areas. This type of tourism includes the following activities:

- Trips to farms;
- Workshops on harvesting and preparation of agricultural products;
- Feeding and care of farm animals;
- Preparation of local crafts and traditional food;
- Learning and participating in ecological and organic farming.

As a result of combining agriculture and tourism through agrotourism, not only agricultural activities will expand, but also the employment of the population in rural areas will increase, and tourists will have the opportunity to closely study rural culture.

The impact of agrotourism on agriculture is reflected in several main directions:

Agrotourism creates an additional source of income for agricultural producers. By selling their products directly to tourists, farmers earn not only

income from product sales, but also by providing tourists with the experience of participating in agricultural activities. This type of tourism plays an important role in increasing the added value of agricultural products.

Thanks to agrotourism, infrastructure in rural areas is improved. Due to the influx of tourists, the demand for local infrastructure increases, which creates the need to develop roads, housing, hotels, restaurants and other service networks in rural areas. This process creates new opportunities for economic growth for agricultural producers.

Agrotourism increases the demand for agricultural products in rural areas. In many cases, tourists appreciate the naturalness and ecological purity of agricultural products. This creates an opportunity to sell agricultural products at a higher price in the markets. By branding and certifying local products, agricultural producers may be able to export their products to wider markets.

Agrotourism increases employment among rural residents by creating new jobs in rural areas. This process serves to keep young people in rural areas, reduce migration and encourage them to actively participate in agricultural activities. The income obtained through agrotourism allows to improve the living conditions of agricultural producers.

Tourists visit rural areas and get acquainted with rural life, culture and customs. This contributes not only to economic but also to social development. Local crafts, folk traditions and national dishes are widely promoted through agrotourism, which is important for the preservation and development of rural culture.

The development of agrotourism is aimed at deepening the integration of agriculture and tourism, which ensures the joint growth of these two sectors. In order to develop agrotourism in the future, it is necessary to pay attention to the following directions:

- Development of local infrastructure: It is necessary to expand the

possibilities of attracting tourists by creating the necessary infrastructure for agrotourism.

- Promotion of ecological tourism: It is important to develop ecological tourism aimed at effective use of natural resources in rural areas and their protection.

- Training of agrotourism personnel: It is necessary to increase the efficiency of agrotourism by training qualified specialists in the fields of agriculture and tourism.

Agrotourism has a significant impact on the agricultural economy by successfully combining agriculture and tourism. This type of tourism provides new ways of selling agricultural products, increases employment in rural areas and develops infrastructure. In the future, it will be possible to support the economic and social development of rural areas by expanding agrotourism. The development of agrotourism not only brings additional income to agriculture, but also becomes an important tool in the preservation and promotion of rural culture and traditions.

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